

Motivational Young Entrepreneur's Personal Branding on Instagram: A Modest Crazy Rich Asian

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ABSTRACT: Individuals' personal branding in social media convey meaning with particular signification. Interpretation of the image could rebuild and strengthen an individual's public persona. Putri Tanjung, the CEO of a creative business has carried values as a young inspirational entrepreneur through her contribution and influence on society. This study aims to analyze the meaning of motivational content on the @putri_tanjung Instagram account. This paper discusses the signs and meaning of Putri Tanjung's personal branding using Ferdinand de Saussure semiotics method. The findings show that there is intrinsic meaning in the motivation message presented in the message of each Instagram content selected in this study. The study identified components of personal branding used in the unit analysis which consists of values, skills, and behavior. This paper concludes that despite her family background, she does not represent herself based on the well-known conglomerate family, but as an inspirational individual with a work ethic.

KEYWORDS: Instagram, Meaning, Motivation, Personal branding, Semiotics, Values.

INTRODUCTION

An influencer's personal branding is influential and gives particular meaning based on the signs created through messages which could be thoroughly interpreted and affected the audiences. Social media as the medium of message delivery and a "storefront" of someone's activities and life portrayal is a potential platform to build personal branding with a powerful message in it.

Personal branding involves managing reputation, style, appearance, attitudes, and skills in an orderly and consistent manner. The Instagram platform is an effective target in shaping personal branding because someone can be known to a broader public. Chaniago & Sayuti (2022) discovered that social media is proven to affect entrepreneurial intention among youngsters positively, thus, social media plays a part in quickening the growth of business enterprises among them. Gilani et al (2020) study on the effect of social media usage on entrepreneurial leadership shows that social media usage has influenced entrepreneurial leadership. Thus, social media content on motivation and entrepreneurship has affected those who are being exposed. Communicating messages and information can either be conveyed through words whether spoken or written or through other non-verbal means (Kadim & Abbas, 2022).

In building personal branding on Instagram social media, an individual must know the differentiation in the form of advantages or uniqueness that he or she has, and be consistent with what they are doing to instill a strong impression on Instagram users (Mulyana et al., 2020). Becoming an influencer means he or she has to do the work full of thought since they are intentionally constructing personal branding (Vasconcelos & Rua, 2021).

In order to create the content, they have to make a proper plan and consider the impact of their actions on others. Thus, the role of an influencer in constructing their personal branding in a motivational way could be cultivated among the followers is crucial, in this case regarding the entrepreneurial profession. Social media can create a person's self-image or personal branding with a positive or negative impression. The image represents a person's beliefs, ideas, and impressions of a particular object (Ruslan, 2008). The notions of beliefs, ideas, and impressions presented could reflect their social identity as well. The inner core of culture is made up of the history, identity, beliefs, values, and worldviews of a cultural group (Dodd, 1998).

Ifada and Mufidah (2019) once studied the representations of people with tremendous wealth in the movie entitled Crazy Rich Asians. It is portrayed that the identity expression is reflected in the consumption pattern through food, fashion, and luxury ownership. Similar studies towards the movies have also been conducted by questioning the representation of the Crazy Rich Asians in the movie (Zhao, 2019; Le & Kang, 2019). When the stereotype of Crazy Rich Asians is constructed in such a way displaying

their wealthiness, this paper is focusing on a young influencer who was born in a conglomerate family who has tremendously influenced Indonesian youngsters through her movements with modest presentation in social media.

The influencer who is widely known on Instagram as a young-successful entrepreneur is Putri Indahsari Tanjung or, in short, addressed as Putri Tanjung. She started her first career in the creative world in junior high school, namely making an event organizer called El-Paradiso. Then, Putri started her business under the name Creativepreneur at the age of 17. She is active in social activities and has an interest in the growth of MSMEs in Indonesia. In 2019, she was appointed as one of the Millennial Special Staff to assist the President of the Republic of Indonesia. Besides, she also won the Women Who Shape Indonesia Today from the Ziliun platform in 2015 and contributed as an inspirational and motivational speaker at various events (Atmasari, 2019).

Through her Instagram account @putri_tanjung, she often shares valuable moments in her life so that she can inspire her followers, such as being a speaker at several events, creating Creativepreneur Corner events in several cities in Indonesia, moments when Putri Tanjung is in a meeting, visiting entrepreneurial activities in one city. in Banyuwangi, and productive activities at home. She has 859 thousand followers on her Instagram account as of September 2022. As the CEO of the company, she is very productive as a creativepreneur. Coming from well-known family background, Putri has been exposed to entrepreneurial experience since a young age. Her conglomerate family background has shaped her to be a more creative and hard-work individual.

In the modern era, the development of technology and the Internet is increasingly fast and sophisticated, making it easy for everyone to obtain or disseminate information, discuss and share thoughts with others. Based on the information above, it can be concluded that currently, Instagram is a social media that is highly used by the public. Instagram has exciting features that attract users for instance the filters/effects in the Instagram story that beautify the video or photos posted. Various exciting features available on Instagram make it easy for users to capture moments of daily activities for other users, provide information, do business and form a self-image.

The content uploaded at Putri Tanjung's Instagram account presents inspirational and wise words that could make people enthusiastic and motivated. This makes motivation interesting to study because there are signs and meanings using the semiotic analysis method of Ferdinand de Saussure who represents a young CEO who is active in entrepreneurship on Instagram accounts. Based on the background of Putri's family and her role as an impactful young entrepreneur, it is intriguing to see how her Instagram content has shaped her image as a young motivator and successful young entrepreneur. The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Observing the content and captions on the Instagram account @putri_tanjung.
2. Interpreting the activity of posting a photo of @putri_tanjung which indicates there is a motivating caption in building personal branding.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication and Semiotics

The essence of communication is the process of statements between humans, the information is in the form of one's thoughts or feelings to others by using language as a tool of conveying message (Effendy, 2003). From the above understanding, it can be concluded that the notion of communication is a message that is conveyed by the communicator (message sender) to the communicant (message recipient) using media channels/tools so that it can influence someone to do something (feedback). According to Pratminingsih (2006), communication has elements, including:

1. The source of information is the person who conveys the message. At this stage, the basis of information carries out a complex process consisting of the emergence of a stimulus that creates thoughts and desires to communicate. These thoughts are encoded into messages, and the message is conveyed through channels or media to the recipient.
2. Encoding is a process in which the central nervous system of the information source instructs the information source to select understandable symbols that can describe the message.
3. The message is anything that has meaning for the recipient. The news is the result of the encoding process. This message can be in words, facial expressions, voice pressure, and appearance.
4. Media is a method or equipment used to convey messages to recipients. The media can be in the form of letters, telephone or face to face.

Message is not equal to meaning (Danesi, 2010). Furthermore, Danesi quoted Saussure that explained a sign as a binary structure which consists of two component 1) physical/signifier and 2) conceptual/signified. Etymologically, the term semiotic

comes from the Greek word "semeion" which means "sign". The sign itself is defined as something which, on the basis of previously established social conventions, can be considered to represent something else (Umberto: 2015). It is basically the science of interpreting signs that objects not only carry information, but objects communicate by constructing signs. This study employed Saussure's model of the sign which is the dyadic tradition of semiotics. Semiotics concerns with the meaning of a message and how it is delivered through signs (Danesi, 2010).

Focusing on linguistic signs, Saussure explained that a sign is composed of a signifier and a signified. As quoted by Chandler (2005), Saussure (1983, 66) stated that *"a linguistic sign is not a link between a thing and a name, but between a concept [signified] and a sound pattern [signifier] as presented in Figure 1. The sound pattern is not actually a sound; for a sound is something physical. A sound pattern is the hearer's psychological impression of a sound, as given to him by the evidence of his senses. This sound pattern may be called a 'material' element only in that it is the representation of our sensory impressions. The sound pattern may thus be distinguished from the other element associated with it in a linguistic sign. This other element is generally of a more abstract kind: the concept."*

Figure 1. Saussure's model of the sign

Source: Chandler (2005) based on Saussure (1976, 158)

Therefore, language is the material aspect of what language is said or heard and what is written and read. Signifier refers to meaningful sounds or meaningful scribbles (material aspects), namely what is said and what is written or read, while signified refers to mental images, namely thoughts or concepts of mental aspects of language (Sobur: 2003). In the Saussurean model, the sign is the whole that result from the association of the signifier and the signified, while the relationships between those two is referred as signification Chandler (2005). There are several principles of semiotics according to Saussure's semiotics model as follows (Pilliang: 2003):

1. Structural principles, where the sign is seen as a unity between something material and conceptual. And the focus is on the relationship of these elements so it produces a meaning.
2. The principle of unity (unity). A sign is a unit that cannot be separated between the signified fields in the form of concepts, idea, ideas, meanings, and the material or concrete signifier fields, namely in the form of writing, images, sounds, objects. They are like two sides of a coin that cannot be separated.
3. Conventional principles (conventional). That is in the form of social agreement about language (signs and meanings) among language communities.
4. The principle of synchronic (synchronic). That is a study of signs as a system that remains in the context of time which is considered constant, stable and unchanging.
5. The principle of representation. That is a sign represents a reality, which will be the reference. A flower sign, for example, represents something in the world of reality, so the relationship between the sign and reality is more representative.
6. The principle of continuity (continuity). Namely, the relationship between the sign system and its users socially in language, is continuous and never changes, so that in it there is no possibility of radical changes in signs, codes, and meanings, except for very small changes.

According to Rusdy (2015), there are four (4) important points of Saussure's model as the following points:

1. *Signifier dan Signified*

Saussure's theory is the principle that language is a sign system, and each sign is composed of two parts, namely the signifier and the signified. Signifier is a material aspect of language in the form of sounds and scribbles and has meaning about what will be written, read or heard. Signified description of mental, thought and language. The relationship between the signifier and the signified together forms a sign, both of which cannot be separated from each other, so that they form a unity.

2. *Langue dan parole*

Parole is the activity of speaking, while langue is the abstract underlying parole. Saussure analogizes langue with a dictionary that every language user has. Parole is the use of language individually. If the relationship between langue and parole is analogous to the wayang performance, the period of the wayang storyline is generally the dictionary (langue), while the disclosure of wayang stories by the puppeteers with their respective characteristics is parole.

3. *Synchronic dan Diachronic*

Synchronic is the study of signs at a point in time, usually the present. Diachronic is a search about changes in the meaning and form of signs in the development of time. Danesi exemplifies diachronic analysis by looking at the word person (personal).

4. *Syntagmatic dan associative*

One more language structure discussed in Saussure's basic conception of the system of distinction between signs is about syntagmatic and associative (paradigmatic), or between syntagmatic and paradigmatic. This relationship is found in words as a series of sounds and concept words.

Saussure himself concentrates more on the langue and parole paradigms. Langue is the entire sign system that functions as a means of verbal communication between members of a language community, abstract in nature. According to Saussure, langue is the totality of a set of facts of a language, which is inferred from the memory of language users and is a linguistic storehouse that exists in each individual. Langue exists in the brain, not just an abstraction and is a social symptom. With this langue, a speech community is formed, namely a community that agrees on grammatical, vocabulary, and pronunciation rules.

Furthermore, what is meant by parole is the use or realization of langue by each member of the language community is concrete because parole is nothing but a physical reality that differs from one person to another. Parole is personal, dynamic, agile, social, occurs at a certain time, place, and atmosphere. Saussure's rule is additionally known as structuralism and has given the essential center to the mind of prominent scholars in the other areas, and one of the foremost imperatives is the approach of structuralism by Levi-Strauss (Yakin & Totu, 2014). In a nutshell, Saussure's model of sign gives more accentuation to inside structure committed to cognitive thought process or action of human minds in organizing the physical or intangible signs of their environments, and among them is the structure of linguistic signs within the language system that allows them to operate as human creatures and communicate with one another.

Motivation

Hanafiah and Suhana (2009) explain that motivation can be divided into two, namely intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation:

1. Intrinsic motivation is the motivation that comes from within the individual without any external stimulation.
2. Extrinsic motivation is motivation from outside such as praises, grading until presents and gifts and external factors with impetus motivational

Personal Branding

Personal Branding comes from personal, which means personal, and branding, which means making a brand or brand itself. Consciously or not, activities carried out daily are the formation of personal branding, because everyone can have a brand or *image*. Personal Branding can make everyone sees you with a unique and different character (Ievansyah & Sadono, 2018).

Personal branding is defined as process where people and their careers are marked as brand (Karaduman, 2013). Additionally, in personal branding development, individual tries to manage others' impression of their skills, abilities and experiences (Johnson, 2017). Meanwhile Monthoya and Vandehey as cited in McNally & Speak (2004) explain that a personal brand can emerge from various aspects, both values, personality, expertise and other uniquenesses possessed. Therefore, a brand can be considered as a form of one's commitment to the general public. From this commitment, the expectations of others about

someone spontaneously emerge into something that must be realized and in accordance with reality. The more a person can display a self-image in accordance with the perceptions of others, the greater the trust that other people place in him.

Parengkuan and Tumewu as cited in Haroen (2014) stated that there are three components of personal branding, as follows:

- 1) The values that exist in a person and are consistently displayed to others will be attached to other people's thoughts about themselves
- 2) The skills, someone doing a certain job, the stronger the personal brand he has in communicating his skills to others effectively.
- 3) The behavior, in building a personal brand, one must make various efforts to support the formation of a personal brand, these efforts must be in line with the personal branding that you want to build and run consistently.

Social Media for Personal Branding

The rapid development of communication and information technology has made the world feel wider so that there is no distance in spare time. With the increasing use of the internet and also supported by information and telecommunications technology, there is a convergence of pre-existing media known as new media. Technologies described as "new media" are digital, and often have the characteristics of being manipulable, networkable, dense, free, interactive, and impartial. New Media or online media is defined as a product of technology-mediated communication that is shared with digital computers (Creeber & Martin, 2009).

In this digital era, various media choices can be used, such as television, print media and even online media. Moreover, social media is a tool in conveying or conveying information to the public the need for information at this time, making people prefer media that is easily and quickly accessed to get information (Pellizzaro, 2018). The development of the internet has required companies to employ various digital media options (Dwityas et al., 2020), which also could be considered by individuals self in order to build their self branding. Social media is a media platform that focuses on the existence of users who facilitate their activities and collaboration (Geni et al., 2021).

Therefore, social media can be seen as an online medium (facilitator) that could possibly strengthens relationships between users and a social bond (Van Dijk: 2016). Askalani (2012) explains that social media users are divided into 2, namely:

1. Active users: users perform activities such as commenting on photo or status posts and sending messages to each other in chat application
2. Passive users: users check applications on social media, visit websites and just view pictures, photos or other entertainment

The new media that was present was Instagram. Instagram is taken from the word 'Insta', which originally came from 'Instant' and 'gram' from the word 'telegram' (Ghazali: 2016). So Instagram is a combination of the words Instant-Telegram, which can be interpreted as an application to send information quickly, namely in the form of photos and videos. The use of this application is increasing because of the advantages offered by the various features of the Instagram application. The central part that makes Instagram popular is the presence of filters already in the application, and there are caption, comment and like features.

Self branding involves individual developing a distinctive public image for commercial gain and/or cultural capital (Khamis & Willing, 2016). The central point of personal branding is the idea that individual benefit from having a public identity that is singularly charismatic and responsive to the needs and interests of target audience. The idea of self-branding has actually permeated in manu literatures since 1920s with regards to self-improvement and a positive attitude.

RESEARCH METHOD

In order to analyze the signs in the unit analysis selected in this study, semiotics model proposed by Ferdinand de Saussure is the method employed for this study. As shown in Figure 2, the signs identified in the unit analysis of this study were analyzed as the component of signifier and signified which further be interpreted as signification whereby construct meaning.

(Sumber: McQuail, 2000)

Figure 2. Saussure’s model

Source: McQuail (2000)

Unit Analysis

The unit of analysis in this study is the content on the Instagram account @putri_tanjung. This study analyzes Putri Tanjung content uploads in writing captions that have motivational meanings so that they represent personal branding through Instagram. The unit analysis chosen are based on several selected Instagram contents uploaded on @putri_tanjung Instagram account which attracted a lot of sympathy and provided many motivational sentences for his followers. The author determines the research period from January 24, 2019 - September 29, 2020. This study has chosen four (4) posts of Putri Tanjung moments that reflect her personal branding, and assumed to provide motivational meaning in the caption. The author chooses Putri Tanjung content posts for the last one year with four (4) contents selected based on their background and the sympathetic appeal of their followers, the selected content moments are:

Tabel 1. Unit Analysis

DATA NO	CONTENT	DATE
D1	As Speaker at an Event	January 24 th 2019
D2	Banyuwangi Visit	February 22 nd 2020
D3	Creativepreneur Event	April 21 st 2020
D4	Productive Activities at Home	September 29 th 2020

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section will be presenting the data, analysis and discussion. Four (4) unit analyses have been identified and further be analyzed using semiotics method by Saussure. Following is the data analysis for this study:

Figure 3. D1: Speaker at an event

Source: Instagram @putri_tanjung

Caption: “I believe that ‘pressure creates diamond’. Every individual has the urge to develop themselves. The fact that I can give a platform for Indonesia youngsters to be entrepreneur is one of my motivations. Therefore, I establish @creativepreneur that I run with #JalaninBareng my team with the mission to spread the entrepreneurship “virus” to the youngsters to promote the nation. The key is that never be afraid to start. Seek for your own motivation and be meaningful for others :) What have you been doing to move forward?”

Explanation: Languge as a self-motivating flow in entrepreneurship while Parole revealed at the beginning of forming creativepreneur activities. Seen in the comments, this content is written in a way to motivating which categorized into the category of intrinsic motivation. Based on the personal branding component of content, it falls into skills component of personal branding, namely being able to do something that is done effectively. The colour she choose for her outfit showing modesty and professionalism that what she is trying to represent is her ideas and creativities, not the appearance.

Figure 4. D2: Visit to Banyuwangi
Source: Instagram @putri_tanjung

Caption: “this Friday, I have felt the energy of Banyuwangi people. The short visit to Banyuwangi has proven tremendous stories on how this city has transformed to be one of the most moving forward in tourism and creative economy industries...”

Explanation: Languge as an excitement in #nongkibar activities in Banyuwangi while Parole is a youth activity with creativity carried out. The caption stated that being a young person should not be afraid of failure and must be ready to doing things, hence take risks is one of it. This content could fall under component of the skill in personal branding. Being able to do work or activities consistently and communicate their skills to others effectively are they key points. The closeness with audiences are one of the sign showing that there is proximity between her and the society she visited.

Figure 5. D3: Creativepreneur Event
Source: Instagram @putri_tanjung

Caption: *“I’ve always believed that women have important role to the better changed by being unlimitedly productive. The demands lay upon women to be a perfect individual with all the role and responsibilities attached have make them special. In my opinion, women are terrific in every way. Women can be a great figure in any circumstances as family, work, business...”*

Explanation: Languas as Kartini Day, while Parole understands Kartini day according to the industrial worker side. This content falls into the category of intrinsic motivation due to encouragement of women empowerment. Based on the caption written, the content falls into the component of behavior in personal branding. The role of her being in the center among the co-workers showing her participation and her importance as part of the team. This is how the value of equality is shown.

Figure 6. D4: Being productive at home

Source: Instagram @putri_tanjung

Caption: *“Afternoon thoughts: I am grateful that has been granted great opportunity to work harder, be smarter, and be faster as the gesture of my gratitude of the blessings and responsibilities I have given. Let’s continue to be kind and responsible to carry out our responsibilities. Stay healthy and be positive in every situation”*

Explanation: Languas as a reminder of yourself, while Parole tells stories in the afternoon during work activities. Based on the caption written, the content falls into the component of values in personal branding. The content display her causal life which still showing her doing her work and being productive. The content falls into the category of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, that is, the presence of an inner or outer impulse that is able to motivate in the way that is carried out. The caption that was written reminds that gratitude is important in carrying out any activity because with it a person can understand the obligations in carrying out his duties properly. In a way she shows her work ethic, yet she is still representing herself being humble and modest.

Based on the above description of data analysis, we will further be discussing the findings by interpreting the meaning of signs presented in the unit analysis; i.e., contents of @putri_tanjung Instagram which contain motivational values. The meaning of motivation in this study can be seen in some of the content uploaded by Putri Tanjung on her Instagram account. Event and activities carried out such as being a resource person at an event, activity visits, *creativepreneur* activities and productivity at home. The activities carried out by Putri Tanjung were able to inspire her followers. In the contents selected which uploaded by at Putri Tanjung’s Instagram account, she displays the personal branding component through her behavior and skills. From the categorization from the data analysis, following are the discussion of the findings:

As someone who is known and the child of a conglomerate, Putri Tanjung is not a person who likes to be social and remains a simple person because she does not want to show her wealth. Putri Tanjung is someone who has a sense of ambition when doing something. In the midst of being busy, Putri Tanjung does not waste time and can manage it well. For example, when working as a special staff for the president and CEO of the company she owns. Here are 4 contents that show the 3 components of Putri Tanjung’s personal branding, namely values, skills and behavior (Parengkuan and Tumewu in Haroen, 2014).

First, the value component, which is related to the beliefs, preferences, and passions you have. Value as something that grows and takes root in a person can shape and play a major role in every decision and behavior that is carried out. This component can be

seen in the content when Putri Tanjung does her activities at home. As an entrepreneur and CEO, Putri continues to do productive and simple activities even though she is in a rich family. This was shown by Putri when she was young, she used the best time possible, so that what she did becomes a good thing, especially impact others. If the need for what is done can be a motivation for yourself not to stop learning.

Second of all is the skill component, which is what is used to do, do, or produce in a particular job. Communication skills are needed to communicate skills possessed to others effectively and clearly. This component can be seen in the content of being a speaker at an event and visiting Banyuwangi. Being an entrepreneur and special staff for the president is an achievement for Putri Tanjung, because both jobs are in the scope of entrepreneurship according to her background. This can make it easier for Putri Tanjung in conveying clear and direct information. With two different responsibilities at work, Putri must be able to manage herself as best as possible consistently.

The third one is behavioral components which are regarding how she does to create a personal brand so that other people will see behavior that reflects her as a positive value in the eyes of others. This component can be seen in the content of creativepreneur event activities. In the content, Putri explained about Kartini Day, in which Putri Tanjung was the only woman among her male friends. That being a woman who is not dominant in a group does not mean that she cannot provide innovation and aspirations. Therefore, the selected moments with written captions are interconnected. Self branding involves individual developing a distinctive public image for commercial gain and/or cultural capital (Khamis & Willing, 2016).

Despite her background as entrepreneur, she is presenting herself differently; impactful to the society. She promotes equality and empowerments among others; that every individual has to keep on productive in a way to contribute to the nation. The content also proves that there are equal rights, as women must also be able to work in various fields for better change. As Hanafiah and Suhana (2009) explain that intrinsic motivation is the motivation that comes from within the individual without any external stimulation, this content is reflecting the intrinsic motivation as well. This is assumed rooted from the values in the family. As Dodd (1998) stated that the inner core of culture is made up of the history, identity, beliefs, values, and worldviews of a cultural group, Putri Tanjung has a strong roots of her values in building her personal branding.

From all the content posted by Putri Tanjung, it forms a motivational construction in her personal branding. It has also seen in the interpretation of each caption of every picture posted. With this, the purpose of personal branding is how the other person has a positive view or positive perception so that it can continue to trust or other actions. once studied the representations of people with tremendous wealth in the movie entitled Crazy Rich Asians. She does not show herself as a crazy rich Asian from a well-known conglomerate family as her identity. It is contradicted with the identity expression portrayal at the famous Crazy Rich Asians movie which are reflected in the consumption pattern through food, fashion, and luxury ownership (Ifada and Mufidah, 2019). The makeup, the outfit, ambience and words given are showing motivation and strong personality of young inspirational entrepreneur.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study can be concluded as follows:

1. From the content and captions uploaded by Putri Tanjung on her Instagram account, there are components of personal branding employed which consisting of values, skills and behavior.
2. As a person successful at a young age, Putri Tanjung is presenting herself in a simple manner and motivational. A visionary individual who does not represent the well-known conglomerate family but an inspirational work ethic.

Based on the analyzed contents, there is a meaning of intrinsic motivation, which means that the biggest motivation is oneself. This paper concludes that despite her family background, Putri Tanjung presents herself as a modest, motivational, and inspirational self to her followers. This study gives implications to the personal branding development among individual that impactful, motivational and inspirational in the context of cultivating the young entrepreneur. The strength of individuals' values, skills and behavior as part of personal branding components should be taken into account.

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